

Aortic Valve Neocuspidization (Ozaki Procedure) in Georgia: A Five-Year Single-Center Experience

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Abstract

Background:

Aortic valve neocuspidization (AVNeo), or the Ozaki procedure, is an emerging surgical technique involving the reconstruction of the aortic valve using glutaraldehyde-treated autologous pericardium. It presents a promising alternative to mechanical or bioprosthetic valve replacement, especially in younger patients and those contraindicated for long-term anticoagulation [1,2].

Objective:

To evaluate short- and mid-term outcomes of the Ozaki procedure performed at a tertiary cardiac surgery center in Georgia over a five-year period.

Methods:

A retrospective analysis was conducted of 101 patients (mean age 57.7 ± 9.3 years, 52 males) who underwent AVNeo between 2016 and 2021. Indications included stenosis (63%), regurgitation (7%), and mixed disease (30%). Valve types included tricuspid (73), bicuspid (26), and unicuspid (2). Surgical techniques included isolated AVNeo (56 cases), AVNeo CABG (24), and combined procedures.

Results:

Mean preoperative valve gradient was 51.9 ± 7.1 mmHg with mean valve area 0.78 ± 0.12 cm². Postoperatively, EF improved (53.9% to 56.8%), with significant reduction in gradient (5.3 ± 2.6 mmHg). Hospital mortality was 2.15%, with a mean follow-up of 28 months. AVNeo demonstrated high hemodynamic performance, no requirement for lifelong anticoagulation, reproducibility, and low incidence of complications. It was especially advantageous in patients with small aortic annulus or infective endocarditis.

Conclusion:

This report represents Georgia's first documented series on the Ozaki procedure. Our results confirm AVNeo as a safe, effective, and cost-efficient alternative to traditional valve replacement in selected patient populations, aligning with international outcomes [3-5].

Keywords

AVNeo (Aortic Valve Neocuspidization with Glutar-Aldehyde Treated Pericardium), Ozaki Procedure, Aortic Valve Disease, Autologous Pericardium, Georgia

Conflict of Interest

None declared.

References

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